

EXPERIENCE OF STENTING IN IATROGENIC PERFORATION OF THE ESOPHAGUS IN A PATIENT WITH STAGE III CARDIOSPASM

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Abstract. Currently available treatment options include pneumatic dilation, laparoscopic Geller myotomy, botulinum toxin injections, relaxing the lower esophageal sphincter and esophagectomy in the refractory end stage of the disease. The purpose of the study. Consider the possibility of stenting as a method of closing the defect of the esophageal wall in its iatrogenic damage. Material and methods. In this report, we present a clinical case of a patient with cardiospasm II-III art., complicated by iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall after pneumatic cardiodilation. Conclusion. The use of esophageal, self-expanding, fully coated stents with an antireflux valve in patients with cardiospasm complicated by iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall is a good alternative to emergency surgery in the first hours after iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall.

Keywords: esophagus; laparoscopic myotomy; stenting; pneumatic cardiodilation.

Relevance: Currently available treatment options include pneumatic dilation, laparoscopic Geller myotomy, botulinum toxin injections, relaxing the lower esophageal sphincter and esophagectomy in the refractory terminal stage of the disease. A formidable complication of minimally invasive treatment of neuromuscular diseases is iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall, requiring emergency surgery. However, suturing the defect of the damaged esophageal wall against the background of a purulent-inflammatory process does not always lead to success. As a result, new methods of restoring the integrity of the damaged esophageal wall are being considered. The article describes a clinical case of successful treatment of iatrogenic damage to the abdominal esophagus using a self-expanding metal stent.

The purpose of the study: consider the possibility of stenting as a method of closing the defect of the esophageal wall in its iatrogenic damage.

Material and methods: in this report we present a clinical case of a patient with cardiospasm II-III art., complicated by iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall after pneumatic cardiodilation.

Results and discussion: Patient B., 27 years old, H/D No. 4402, was hospitalized in the department of surgery of the esophagus and stomach on 26.10.2020. with the diagnosis - The Main one: Cardiospasm of II-III degree. Related: Oligophrenia I art. Peptic ulcer of the 12th duodenum. Complaints upon admission: dysphagia on solid and thick food, pain behind the sternum during meals, weight loss of 2-3 kg within 7 months, general weakness. The diagnosis of Cardiospasm II-III art. was established on the basis of complaints, instrumental research methods. During the second session of pneumatic cardiodilation under X-ray control on 28.10.2020, during the cardiostatator, against the background of inadequate behavior of the patient, who began to resist the manipulation, iatrogenic damage to the abdominal esophagus occurred. In this regard, after a preliminary short-term preoperative preparation, the patient was operated on on 28.10.2020 in an emergency during the first 3 hours. Laparotomy was performed. Suturing of the right wall of the abdominal esophagus. Sanitation, drainage and tamponing of the abdominal cavity. In the postoperative period, the patient was repeatedly X-rayed, while there was a contrast swelling along the right wall of the abdominal esophagus. In this regard, on the 20th day after the operation (11/17/2020), a metal (nitinol), self-expanding, fully polyurethane-coated stent with an antireflux valve, manufactured by Flextent, China, 60 mm long, 26 mm in diameter, was installed endoscopically along the conductor string, in order to close the esophageal defect. After the stent was installed, X-ray control was performed, there was no contrast congestion. The patient was discharged home, the power per os was restored in full. On 22.12.2020, the patient was re-hospitalized in the department of surgery of the esophagus and stomach and does not complain of dysphagia. I did not notice an increase in body temperature for a month. On 12/24/2020, an endoscopic removal of a previously installed stent was performed. On 12/24/2020, a radiography of the esophagus with a water-soluble contrast was made - a trazograph of 76%-20 ml. There is no contrast congestion. Contrast freely enters the stomach. Radiological picture of cardiospasm of the I st.

Conclusion: the use of esophageal, self-expanding, fully coated stents with an antireflux valve in patients with cardiospasm complicated by iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall is a good alternative to emergency surgery in the first hours after iatrogenic damage to the esophageal wall.

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